

THE SECOND CONSTANT OF SMARANDACHE

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In the present note we prove that the sum of remarkable series $\sum_{n \geq 2} \frac{S(n)}{n!}$, which implies the Smarandache function is an irrational number (second constant of Smarandache).

Because $S(n) \leq n$, it results $\sum_{n \geq 2} \frac{S(n)}{n!} \leq \sum_{n \geq 2} \frac{1}{(n-1)!}$. Therefore the series $\sum_{n \geq 2} \frac{S(n)}{n!}$ is convergent to a number f .

Proposition. The sum f of the series $\sum_{n \geq 2} \frac{S(n)}{n!}$ is an irrational number.

Proof. From the precedent lines it results that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{i=2}^n \frac{S(i)}{i!} = f$. Against all reason we assume that $f \in \mathbb{Q}$, $f > 0$. Therefore it exists $a, b \in \mathbb{N}$, $(a, b) = 1$, so that $f = \frac{a}{b}$.

Let p be a fixed prime number, $p > b$, $p \geq 3$. Obviously, $\frac{a}{b} = \sum_{i=2}^{p-1} \frac{S(i)}{i!} + \sum_{i \geq p} \frac{S(i)}{i!}$ which leads to:

$$\frac{(p-1)!a}{b} = \sum_{i=2}^{p-1} \frac{(p-1)!S(i)}{i!} + \sum_{i \geq p} \frac{(p-1)!S(i)}{i!}$$

Because $p > b$ it results that $\frac{(p-1)!a}{b} \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\sum_{i=2}^{p-1} \frac{(p-1)!S(i)}{i!} \in \mathbb{N}$. Consequently we have $\sum_{i \geq p} \frac{(p-1)!S(i)}{i!} \in \mathbb{N}$ too.

Be $\alpha = \sum_{i \geq p} \frac{(p-1)!S(i)}{i!} \in \mathbb{N}$. So we have the relation

$$\alpha = \frac{(p-1)!S(p)}{p!} + \frac{(p-1)!S(p+1)}{(p-1)!} - \frac{(p-1)!S(p-2)}{(p-2)!} + \dots$$

Because p is a prime number it results $S(p) = p$.

So

$$\alpha = 1 + \frac{S(p-1)}{p(p-1)} + \frac{S(p-2)}{p(p-1)(p-2)} + \dots > 1 \tag{1}$$

We know that $S(p+i) \leq p+i$ ($\forall i \geq 1$), with equality only if the number $p+i$ is prime. Consequently, we have

$$\alpha < 1 + \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{p(p+1)} + \frac{1}{p(p+1)(p+2)} + \dots < 1 + \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{p^2} + \frac{1}{p^3} \dots = \frac{p}{p-1} < 2 \quad (2)$$

From the inequalities (1) and (2) it results that $1 < \alpha < 2$, impossible, because $\alpha \in \mathbb{N}$. The proposition is proved.

REFERENCES

[1] **Smarandache Function Journal** , Vol.1 (1990), Vol. 2-3 (1993), Vol. 4-5 (1994), Number Theory Publishing, Co., R. Emler Editor, Phoenix, New York, Lyon.

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